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Historical Sciences

THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN THE USSR IN 1960-1985 YEARS

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Abstract

The article examines the domestic physical culture and sports in the 1960s-1980s. It is obvious that before the collapse of the USSR, the physical culture movement in the country developed very successfully. The most significant achievements in the development of mass physical culture and sports of the highest achievements occurred in the 1960s - the first half of the 1980s, when the state began to pay much more attention to physical culture issues than before, and the physical culture movement acquired a more planned and organized character. The central regions of the country, perhaps more fully, more noticeably than other Russian territories, demonstrated the dynamism of the physical culture movement based on a combination of state support with local initiative.

Keywords: sports, history, USSR, movement, society.

I. INTRODUCTION

As the world civilization developed, physical education occupied an increasingly significant place in the life of peoples and each person individually. From the 70s - 80s. of the last century, when sports societies and

clubs began to be created in many countries, and especially since 1896, when the Frenchman P. de Coubertin laid the foundation for the modern Olympic movement, sports contacts were increasingly included in the sphere of international relations. The prestige of national sports directly affects the authority of the state, its place in the world community, and the patriotism of its citizens. Sports activities, like nothing else, help self-affirmation, the formation of a person, allow her to realize her physical and intellectual abilities. In addition, it should be borne in mind that for millions of sports fans, competitions are an attractive spectacle, a magnificent performance with strong feelings, an opportunity to communicate with their idols.

II. METHODOLOGY

The study of the problem posed necessitated the combination of various methodological approaches, the use of heuristic possibilities of ideas contained in various sociological and philosophical-historical theories, primarily in Marxist, as well as the "new social history" and the "School of Annals". The solution of the tasks set in the article predetermined the need to address the issues of general culture, the mentality of Soviet society in the 1960s -1980s.

The main research methods used were problematic, chronological, comparative-historical, systemic, historical-genetic, and in some cases methods of sociology and social psychology. The source base was published and unpublished documents" materials of periodicals, sports museums and rooms, memories of sports veterans. Documents of the highest authorities, including special party-government resolutions - 1966, 1972, 1981. and others, which set out the theoretical and organizational principles and activities of sports societies and organizations. Materials on physical culture and sports take place in statistical yearbooks on the development of the national economy of the USSR and the RSFSR for 1960 -1985.

III. DISCUSSION

The question of the place of physical culture in society and its social role is rooted in the depths of human history. Even in the works of the ancient Greek scientists Plato, Aristotle, Democritus, Socrates, Hippocrates, there are valuable judgments about the benefits of physical exercise, about physical culture as an integral part of upbringing and education. Much attention was paid to this problem by Russian scientists and prominent public figures V.N. Tatishchev, M.V. Lomonosov, P.A. Zagorsky, M.Ya. Novikov, K.D. Ushinsky, D.Y. Pisarev. Academician A.P. Protasov in 1765 made reports at the Academy of Sciences "On the physical education of children" and "On the need for movement to maintain health." A significant contribution to the theory of physical culture was made by scientists, doctors and teachers N.I. Pirogov, I.M. Sechenov, I.P. Pavlov, P. F. Desgaft, hygienists E. A. Pokrovsky and E. M. Dementiev.

A special place in the development of the science of physical culture belongs to K. Marx and F. Engels, who laid the foundations of the class theory of physical education. In contrast to the bourgeois concepts that prevailed in the 19th century about the classlessness of physical education, the founders of Marxism proceeded from the fact that education in general and physical education in particular are conditioned by the material conditions of life in society, are determined by social relations and in capitalist society are of a class nature. This idea was formulated most vividly by K. Marx in his work "Capital". The next period in the historiography of the problem covers 1967-1980, when the qualitative growth of the physical culture movement in the USSR, the expansion of international relations of sports organizations coincided with the process of scientific understanding of the history of physical culture in the country and in its individual regions. The party and government decree of August 11, 1966 "On measures for the further development of physical culture and sports" defined as priority areas the study of historical, sociological, theoretical, methodological, psychological, pedagogical, medical, biological, organizational and managerial problems of physical culture and sports.

Scientific research was included in the comprehensive five-year plans approved by the Committee for Physical Culture and Sports under the Council of Ministers of the USSR.

It was in the second half of the 60s - 70s. a solid historical school in the field of physical culture and sports was formed. The works of G.S. Demeter, E.Yu. Zelikson, D.A. Kradman, S.D. Sinitin, F.I. Samoukov, Y.G. Chudinov, G.D. cultures in different social formations, the stages of the genesis of the international and domestic physical culture movement are determined. The historical aspect of physical culture is covered in serious works - "Physical culture and sport in the USSR", "Soviet system of physical education", in seven issues of "Essays on the history of physical culture".

IV. RESULTS

The results of the study show that by the mid-80s. In terms of the main characteristics of the material and technical physical culture base, the USSR was ahead of most countries in the world. For the central regions of the country, more than for other Russian territories, the concentration of stadiums, arenas, swimming pools, halls and other long-term sports facilities in administrative centers and large cities was typical. The physical culture infrastructure developed most intensively in young cities and towns. The creation of a minimum sufficient material base made it possible to successfully solve the issues of physical education of the younger generation, the organization of amateur physical culture and sports of the highest achievements.

During the period under review, the problem of training teachers and physical education teachers, coaches, instructors and other categories of physical education workers was mainly solved. By the mid 80s. In total, more than 500 thousand full-time physical education workers worked in the USSR, most of whom were educated in higher educational institutions of local pedagogical universities, as well as in physical education technical schools and teacher training schools. The educational level of physical culture personnel was 81% with higher and secondary education. The period under review is notable for the appearance of many courageous, energetic and competent organizers of physical culture - teachers, coaches, heads of sports committees and departments.

60-80s were the time of formation of a multifaceted and effective system of scientific, methodological and medical development of the physical culture movement. Among the most significant shortcomings of this activity, one should note a certain gap between theoretical and methodological developments and their implementation in the practice of physical culture, a certain disproportion in the methodological and medical support of mass physical education and elite sports, the lack of popular publications available to amateur athletes. The organization of mass propaganda of physical culture has risen to a higher quality level. In general, during the period under study, the necessary material and humanitarian conditions were created for the development of mass physical culture and elite sports.

The growth processes of mass physical culture in the republics, territories and regions were distinguished by their large scope, the variety of cultivated sports, especially national ones, and the original forms of organization of mass physical culture. In the years under study, thousands of grassroots physical culture teams and sports clubs arose, and physical culture events became an integral part of social activity in educational and production teams of the city and village.

Physical culture classes have organically joined the educational process in preschool institutions and schools. A versatile and organizationally flexible system of physical culture events provided a fairly high level of physical and moral education of the young generation. Active participation in physical culture was taken by students and teachers of universities, secondary specialized educational institutions and vocational schools. It should be noted that a significant number of students were not focused on physical education classes during extracurricular time. However, the main thing was to seriously improve the educational and extracurricular forms of physical education, which resulted in an increase in the mass character of student sports. The number of participants in sports sections and groups in special educational institutions during the study period increased

by 2-3 times. The study showed that physical culture and health-improving activities in combination with medical and preventive activities had a positive effect on the health of workers, improved the moral atmosphere in teams and contributed to an increase in labor productivity.

V. CONCLUSION

Thus, during the study period, a lot of work was done on the development of physical culture, which resulted in a significant rise in mass physical culture and high-performance sports "The most obvious shortcomings of physical culture and sports activities are excessive centralization of physical culture events, not always effective operation of sports facilities, frequent turnover middle-level physical education personnel were replenished with the creativity of thousands of school teachers, teachers, coaches, sports veterans and the help of the public. The physical culture movement, being an integral part of the national physical culture, enriched it with its experience, made an important contribution to the development of Russian and world culture.

In the context of building a democratic society in Russia, the problem of physical culture becomes especially relevant due to the urgent need to develop a long-term concept for the development of mass physical culture and elite sports at the federal and regional levels. Obviously, the improvement of physical culture and sports activities in modern conditions is directly dependent on the ability to use the creative heritage of past years. In this regard, the richest and in many ways universal experience of sports organizations can be applied both in the republics, territories and regions of the regions, and on an all-Russian scale.

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РАЗВИТИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И СПОРТА В СССР В 1960-1985 ГОДЫ

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Аннотация

В статье рассматривается отечественная физическая культура и спорт в 1960-1980-е годы. Очевидно, что до распада СССР физкультурное движение в стране развивалось очень успешно. Наиболее значительные достижения в развитии массовой физической культуры и спорта высших достижений произошли в 1960-е - первой половине 1980-х годов, когда государство стало уделять вопросам физической культуры гораздо больше внимания, чем раньше, а физкультурное движение приобрело более плановый и организованный характер. Центральные регионы страны, возможно, более полно, более заметно, чем другие российские территории, продемонстрировали динамизм физкультурного движения, основанного на сочетании государственной поддержки с местной инициативой.

Ключевые слова: спорт, история, СССР, движение, общество.

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